

Administrative Support and its Effectiveness on Teachers' Professional Contentment and Retention

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Abstract: This study examined the effectiveness of administrative support and its relationship with teachers' professional contentment and retention in rural public elementary schools in Calatrava District I. This addresses the lack of empirical research focusing on rural school settings. Specifically, it assessed administrative support in terms of professional development opportunities, workload management, and stress reduction interventions; teachers' professional contentment in terms of overall satisfaction, well-being, and motivation; and teacher retention as reflected in the intention to stay and commitment to the school. The study also considered recent Department of Education policies, such as the removal of non-teaching administrative tasks, and was aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, specifically SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth). A quantitative correlational research design was employed. Data were collected from 160 teachers selected through stratified random sampling from 22 schools using a validated self-made questionnaire. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. The results revealed that administrative support, teachers' professional contentment, and teacher retention were rated as Very High. Significant positive relationships were found between administrative support and both teachers' professional contentment and retention rates. These findings indicate that strong administrative support systems contribute to improved teacher satisfaction, well-being, motivation, and long-term commitment in rural settings. Based on the findings, a Faculty Development Plan was proposed to strengthen administrative practices related to professional development, workload management, and stress reduction interventions. The plan serves as a practical guide for school administrators to promote teacher growth, workplace well-being, and organizational stability in rural schools.

Keywords: Administrative support, teachers professional contentment, teacher retention, Administration in Education, Calatrava, Philippines, Quantitative Descriptive-Correlational.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

Administrative support is a key factor in teachers' professional contentment and retention worldwide. In the United States, approximately 8% of teachers leave the profession annually due to unsatisfactory working conditions, which disrupt student learning and school stability (Learning Policy Institute, 2020). Supportive leadership enhances teacher well-being and motivation through professional development (Aldosiry, 2022), which strengthens the overall contentment. In turn, such contentment promotes stability, as practices such as fair workload distribution and recognition have been shown to improve retention (Lovison & Mo, 2024).

Across Southeast Asia, teachers' professional experiences are influenced by job security, the work environment, and responsibilities. Oblina and Phoung (2021) identified these factors as key sources of dissatisfaction among basic education teachers. In Malaysia, Silam et al. (2021) highlighted that principals' competencies, including knowledge, skills, and leadership behaviors, are essential for effective school operations and supporting teachers in their roles.

In the Philippine context, many Filipino educators seek employment abroad because of challenging working conditions (Fabella et al., 2022). Public school educators face large classes, limited learning materials, heavy workloads, and administrative duties, which complicate lesson planning and contribute to professional stress (IDinsight & EDCOM2, 2025; DepEd, 2025). A study in Cebu found that teacher retention is strongly affected by stress and workload, whereas supportive leadership and opportunities for professional growth improve engagement and commitment (Anog et al., 2024).

In the local context, public schools in Negros Occidental, including Calatrava District I, struggle with shortages of classrooms (Sunstar, 2023) and teaching staff (Digicast Negros, 2024). These shortages, combined with high administrative workloads, increase pressure on teachers and reduce their capacity to focus on pedagogical responsibilities and instructional planning (Second Congressional Commission on Education, 2025). In response, the Department of Education issued DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, “Immediate Removal of Administrative Tasks of Public School Teachers” on January 26, 2024, aiming to allow teachers to focus more on classroom instruction and enhance their well-being (TeacherPH, 2025). However, the actual impact of this policy remains unclear, highlighting the need for further investigations.

Several studies have examined teachers’ professional contentment and retention, both globally and regionally. These include research on the influence of administrators and work conditions on special education teachers (Aldosiry, 2022), teacher retention and job satisfaction in Philippine private schools (Anog et al., 2024), comparisons of Filipino teachers in the Philippines and U.S. public schools (Fabella et al., 2022), principal leadership competency in Sabah (Silam et al., 2021), investment in the teacher workforce (Lovison & Mo, 2024), and job satisfaction of basic education teachers in Southeast Asia (Oblina & Phuong, 2021). Despite these studies, there is still a lack of empirical research that explores rural public elementary schools, particularly in Calatrava District I, and how recent policy changes, such as the removal of administrative tasks, influence teacher experiences in rural public schools.

This study aimed to determine the level of effectiveness of administrative support, the extent of teachers’ professional contentment in terms of overall satisfaction, well-being, and motivation, and the level of teacher retention as reflected in their intention to stay and commit to their school.

Given the critical role of teacher support, this study aligns with global educational priorities, particularly the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 4 and 8. Teachers are at the heart of shaping young minds, and when they receive meaningful support, they are better able to thrive, both personally and professionally. This directly aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), as well-supported teachers can deliver high-quality instruction, respond to diverse learning needs, and ensure that all students have access to inclusive and equitable education.

In addition, this aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), as creating safe, motivating, and respectful work environments strengthens teachers’ well-being, enhances their intention to stay, and fosters long-term commitment to their schools. Supporting teachers in this way not only retains dedicated educators but also strengthens the learning and growth of a wider community. The findings of this study guided the creation of a Faculty Development Plan for Calatrava District I, ensuring that interventions respond to the actual needs of its teachers.

Review of Literature and Studies

This section presents the conceptual literature and research studies conducted locally and internationally, covering topics related to the current investigation.

Conceptual Literature

On Administrative Support

Administrative support refers to how school leaders guide, manage and assist teachers in fostering a positive and supportive work environment. Key aspects include providing opportunities for professional growth, ensuring fair and transparent workload distribution, and helping them manage stress during demanding periods (Collie, 2023). For example, when administrators clarify priorities and redistribute tasks during busy periods, teachers experience less stress and maintain higher levels of engagement.

Effective administrative support aligns with transformational leadership, in which school leaders act as motivators, coaches, and facilitators, rather than as mere managers. By fostering trust, encouragement, and innovation, these leaders help teachers feel valued and confident in their work. This approach not only improves morale but also cultivates a collaborative school culture in which teachers can thrive (Northouse, 2022).

Professional development is a critical component of administrative support. Continuous training, seminars, and opportunities for further education support the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), which promotes inclusive and equitable education by enhancing teachers' skills and competencies. Research has shown that providing continuous professional development significantly improves teacher retention and well-being (Davis & Park, 2025).

Workload management is another essential aspect of this process. Excessive administrative work reduces teachers' energy for instruction and student engagement, leading to stress and burnout. Workload intensification and "time poverty" undermine instructional quality and professional contentment (Creagh, 2025). Likewise, clear and consistent communication from administrators helped teachers navigate responsibilities more effectively, easing workload pressure and fostering a supportive school environment (Komari et al., 2024).

In the same way, teachers' mental and emotional health was also a top priority. Implementing stress management interventions such as wellness programs, mental health initiatives, and counseling services helps educators cope with job-related stress and improve resilience. When teachers are supported, they can handle professional challenges more effectively and foster a more caring school environment (Beames et al., 2023). Evidence from scoping and systematic reviews highlights effective interventions, including mindfulness-based programs, CBT-derived approaches, resilience training, and peer support groups, which in many studies reduce stress and burnout while enhancing psychological health (Agyapong et al., 2023). Randomized trials further showed that mindfulness training improves teachers' emotional regulation, self-efficacy, and classroom management (de Carvalho et al., 2021). Recognition complements these initiatives by reinforcing teachers' sense of belonging and value. Practices such as appreciation, awards, or public acknowledgement reduce emotional exhaustion and improve over-all well-being (Zheng et al., 2024). Integrating recognition with evidence-based wellness programs foster resilience, reduces burnout, and strengthens long-term satisfaction and retention.

On Teachers' Professional Contentment

Strong leadership in schools is essential, but the support from school administrators plays a critical role in shaping teachers' professional contentment (Sebullen & Jimenez, 2024). Thus, administrative support forms the foundation for professional contentment, influencing overall satisfaction, well-being, and motivation.

Overall satisfaction reflects teachers' sense of fulfillment, belonging, and contentment with their professional role. When administrators actively provide support, teachers' satisfaction increases, enhancing both commitment and engagement at work (Gilbert, 2023). High levels of overall satisfaction contribute to lower turnover, foster collaboration among staff, and cultivate a school environment in which educators can thrive and meaningfully contribute to student learning.

Teachers' well-being, which is vital for sustaining professional contentment, is closely linked to overall satisfaction. Excessive workload, ancillary tasks, and limited rest can cause emotional exhaustion and stress, undermining teachers' effectiveness (Arbia et al., 2023). Leadership that provides guidance and implements supportive policies mitigates these challenges and promotes work-life balance (Magalong & Torreon, 2021). In the Philippine context, DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, emphasizes reducing non-teaching tasks to allow teachers to focus on instruction while maintaining personal and professional balance (Department of Education, 2024). Prioritizing well-being enables teachers to fully engage in their work and maintain their professional satisfaction.

Once well-being is secured, sustaining motivation is essential for long-term professional contentment. Administrators who provide meaningful professional development, recognize achievements, and foster autonomy strengthen teachers' intrinsic motivation (Tria, 2023). Conversely, rigid or overly bureaucratic policies can reduce motivation and engagement (Tirana et al., 2023).

While autonomy promotes professional agencies, it must be balanced with clear guidance and institutional support to prevent inconsistencies in instructional quality and role ambiguity (Pan et al., 2023).

On Teacher Retention

Teacher retention is closely linked to the level of support teachers receive from school administrators. When such support is inadequate, turnover tends to increase. For instance, in Western Australia, 1,279 teachers resigned in 2024 to 2025, the highest recorded in a single year with reports indicating that resignations have more than doubled over the past five years due to workload and workplace pressures (Western Australia Department of Education, 2025).

Similarly, Philippine public schools lost 38,463 teaching and non-teaching personnel in 2023, largely due to administrative workload, insufficient leadership support, a shortage of qualified applicants, and hiring delays, exacerbated by events such as election bans (Commission on Audit, 2024). To address these issues, the Department of Education announced plans in 2025 to renew contracts and hire more than 7,000 administrative staff to reduce teachers' non-instructional tasks, alleviate burnout, and improve morale, ultimately supporting higher retention (Manila Bulletin, 2025).

Internationally, countries are adopting new strategies to minimize teacher turnover. In the United Kingdom, Education Secretary Bridget Phillipson proposed a more flexible work arrangement, allowing teachers to complete tasks such as lesson planning and grading from home. This measure aimed to improve work-life balance while addressing persistent difficulties in maintaining adequate teaching workforce (The Guardian, 2024).

The intention to stay refers to a teachers' willingness to continue employment at their current school over a time (Shi et al., 2023). Research indicates that teachers who perceive high levels of administrative support including opportunities for professional growth, equitable workload distribution, and emotional encouragement demonstrates stronger intention to stay, even under challenging conditions (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2023). Similarly, Engle et al. (2024) found that teachers who experiencing higher levels of leadership engagement and wellbeing were less inclined to leave, emphasizing the role of empowering and supportive school leadership in promoting teacher retention.

Teachers' commitment reflects the psychological attachment and dedication educators feel toward their school. Supportive administrative practices such as providing professional development opportunities, fair workload distribution, and stress interventions enhance commitment and reduce the probability of staff (Zhan et al., 2023). In rural schools with limited resources, administrators who intentionally create supportive environments and prioritize professional growth can strengthen teachers' loyalty and long-term dedication school (Ofori, 2021). Moreover, administrative support not only directly influences satisfaction but also mitigates the effects of occupational stress on retention. For example, teachers facing high workloads are less likely to leave when they perceive

strong leadership engagement and support (Collie, 2023). These findings underscore the dual role of effective leadership in fostering both commitment and retention.

Beyond the institutional and national context, these findings also resonate with global frameworks promoting quality education and decent work. Teacher retention is not only a human resources concern but also a determinant of instructional continuity and student achievement. The effectiveness of administrative support closely supported with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 8 (Decent work and Economic Growth). SDG 4 emphasizes inclusive, equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities, which rely on well-supported, motivated teachers as central agents of change. Meanwhile, SDG 8 promotes productive employment and decent work for all, including educators. This aligns with the ‘decent work’ principles, ensuring teachers have manageable workloads, opportunities for professional growth, and initiatives that promote their well-being. By strengthening administrative support systems, schools not only enhance teachers’ professional contentment and retention but also contribute directly to the achievement of these global objectives (United Nations, 2024).

Related Studies

Foreign Literature

Effective administrative support has been widely recognized as a foundation for teachers’ professional contentment and long-term retention. Adams et al. (2023) emphasize that principals who engaged in meaningful and empathetic dialogue with teachers foster lower levels of emotional exhaustion and higher workplace morale. These findings highlight the importance of genuine administrative care as a core element of effective leadership.

Within this framework, professional development emerged as a critical component of administrative support. Tosun & Bostanci (2024) investigated administrative empathy and mentorship among Turkish educators and revealed that leaders who provided coaching and constructive feedback promoted greater motivation and leadership confidence. This aligned with the professional development dimension of the current study, which posits that growth-oriented administrative practices strengthen teachers’ professional contentment and professional well-being.

Equally essential in administrative support is workload management. Fair distribution of tasks and open communication between administrators and teachers reduce work-related stress. Tran et al. (2023) examined administrative fairness and respect across American public schools and found that transparent leadership and equitable workload management significantly predicted teachers’ intention to stay in their positions. Similarly, Lochmiller et al. (2024) reported that mentoring systems, workload flexibility, and transparent communication were among the strongest predictors of teacher retention in U.S. high-needs schools. In a related Asian context, Nguyen (2024) surveyed 412 Vietnamese secondary teachers and demonstrated that participatory leadership and shared decision-making enhance teachers’ stability and sense of belongingness.

Meanwhile, stress reduction management achieved through counselling interventions, recognition, and emotional support plays a vital role. Such initiatives sustain teacher productivity and well-being (Cervellione et al., 2025; Delgado-Herrada & Garcia-Horta, 2024). Alberts (2024) emphasized that administrators who manage their own stress effectively are more capable of fostering morale and retention among teachers.

These insights collectively affirmed that effective administrative support, encompassing professional development, workload management, and stress reduction management, served as a structural foundation for sustaining teacher well-being and career continuity. This is consistent with Organizational Support Theory, which posits that when teachers perceive genuine care and fairness from administrators, they reciprocate with stronger commitment and improved performance.

Having established the importance of administrative support, it was essential to examine its influence on teachers’ professional contentment, which serves as a key psychological and

motivational outcome of supportive leadership. Beyond administrative structures, literature further underscores how supportive leadership nurtures teachers' professional contentment. Teacher professional contentment encompasses overall satisfaction, well-being, and intrinsic motivation, factors consistently influenced by administrative behavior and institutional climate. Gibert (2023) found that teachers who experienced recognition and trust from school leaders reported stronger professional commitment and overall satisfaction. Relational trust thus emerged as a central factor in enhancing teachers' motivation and sense of purpose. Complementing this, Li et al. (2023) demonstrated in their study of Chinese secondary educators that emotionally intelligent and supportive leadership mitigated burnout while enhancing job satisfaction and psychological well-being. Their findings further demonstrate that administrative empathy and emotional regulation directly contributed to professional fulfillment.

In a similar vein, Solis et al. (2023) explored teacher-being in Spain during the rise of digital education. Their study found that administrative guidance, digital training, and emotional reassurance significantly improved motivation and reduced technostress. These results aligned with the well-being and satisfaction components of this research, suggesting that proactive administrative engagement can buffer occupational stress and enhance teachers' psychological resilience. This pattern revealed that professional contentment flourishes in environments where administrators actively invest in teachers' growth, recognize their contributions, and cultivate supportive interpersonal climates. This aligned with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, both emphasizing that recognition, belongingness, and growth opportunities are central to sustaining job satisfaction and professional fulfillment.

Sustained professional contentment not only enhances teachers' psychological well-being but also lays the groundwork for retention, as satisfied teachers are more likely to remain committed to their institutions. Building on this, numerous studies have demonstrated that when teachers' professional satisfaction and emotional stability are nurtured through supportive administration, their likelihood of remaining in the profession significantly increases.

Teacher retention remains a pressing issue worldwide, with turnover often linked to administrative and organizational conditions. Zhang et al. (2022) analyzed the relationship between burnout, satisfaction, and turnover intentions among East Asian educators and found that overall job satisfaction mediated the connection between emotional exhaustion and teachers' intention to stay. This finding implies that enhancing satisfaction through supportive leadership can indirectly improve retention.

Similarly, studies show that participative, transparent, and authentic leadership practices strengthen teacher trust and job satisfaction and are associated with lower turnover intentions and longer service periods. In Australia, Arnold and Rahimi (2025) found that favorable working conditions, teacher well-being, and supportive leadership significantly reduced teachers' intention to leave their roles. Similarly, a Korean-based analysis found leadership and school culture to be key predictors of teacher job satisfaction (Kang, 2023). In a wider Asian context, Jun et al. (2023) demonstrated that authentic supervisory leadership reduces employees' turnover intentions via perceived supervisor support.

These studies illustrate a consistent link between administrative support, teacher satisfaction, and retention across diverse educational systems. When administrators provide meaningful professional growth opportunities, ensure workload fairness, and foster emotional support, teachers respond with higher morale, stronger commitment, and greater loyalty to the institution. Such reciprocal relationships reflect the principles of Social Exchange Theory, wherein supportive administrative behaviors cultivate mutual trust and long-term engagement. The reviewed foreign literature thus reveals a global pattern: administrative support integrating professional development, workload balance, and stress management enhances teacher contentment, which in turn predicts retention. Leaders who foster trust, provide growth opportunities, and manage demands fairly create environments that sustain teacher satisfaction, longer service, and professional longevity.

Overall, these global findings provide an empirical basis for examining the interrelations among administrative support, teacher contentment, and retention in the rural public school context of Calatrava District I. The literature affirms the relevance of how administrative support shapes teacher contentment and retention within the Philippine educational setting.

Local Studies

Philippine-based studies have consistently emphasized the crucial role of administrative support in shaping positive school environments and teacher outcomes. Anog et al. (2024) examined the relationship between administrative openness, feedback, and professional development among private-school teachers in Cebu City using a quantitative-correlational approach. Their findings revealed that supportive administrative behavior significantly enhanced teacher commitment and satisfaction. Similarly, Janer and Azarias (2024) investigated professional development practices in Ilocos Sur and found that sustained mentoring and regular training sessions improved teachers' motivation and professional competence. Likewise, Raralio (2023) explored the correlation between administrative mentoring, recognition, and instructional performance among teachers in the Cagayan Region, concluding that professional development opportunities and feedback fostered teacher engagement and loyalty. Espra and Valle (2025) reported that school leaders who provided clear guidance and emotional encouragement in Cagayan de Oro schools significantly improved teachers' morale and sense of belonging. Collectively, these studies demonstrate that effective administrative support through workload distribution, opportunities for growth, and recognition of effort creates conditions that strengthen teacher satisfaction and stability in the teaching profession.

After establishing the significance of administrative support, several local studies have examined how such leadership practices translate into teachers' professional contentment, encompassing satisfaction, well-being, and motivation. Perdizo and Tantiado (2025) investigated the factors influencing professional contentment among teachers in Bacolod City and found that administrative communication and recognition were the strongest predictors of job satisfaction and emotional stability.

In parallel, Magtalas (2024) analyzed workload intensity and burnout among elementary teachers using a quantitative design and revealed that heavy administrative workloads reduced motivation and well-being while increasing burnout. This finding provides a quantitative justification for including workload management as a central administrative dimension in the present study's framework on teachers' professional contentment. Building on these findings, Laurencio Jr. and Cabal (2023) discovered that school heads in Zambales who practiced participative and respectful leadership enhanced teachers' sense of belonging, morale, and motivation, reflecting the Filipino cultural values of pakikisama (camaraderie) and paggalang (respect). Moreover, DepEd e-Saliksik revealed that recognition systems, equitable treatment, and open feedback channels significantly improved teachers' well-being and enthusiasm for teaching (Negoso, 2022). Together, these studies affirm that professional contentment is reinforced when administrators exhibit empathy, fairness, consistent communication, and effective workload management, which are the key elements of a supportive school culture.

Local research also highlights the direct influence of administrative practices and teacher satisfaction on retention. Saldevia and Pedroso (2025) analyzed attrition data from private schools and identified a lack of recognition and weak administrative systems as major factors behind teacher turnover. In a related study, Rafols and Pedroso (2025) found that administrative empathy and fair workload among Batangas elementary teachers significantly reduced turnover intentions and enhanced career commitment. Ramirez and Capili (2024) revealed that transformational leadership behaviors among public-school administrators in Tuguegarao City such as participative decision-making and teacher recognition were strongly linked to teachers' desire to remain in the profession. Likewise, Francisco et al. (2024) discovered that excessive non-teaching workloads in Leyte schools increased stress and attrition risk, underscoring the importance of equitable workload management for teacher retention. These studies underscore that sustained teacher commitment is

achieved when administrators promote fairness, provide recognition, and maintain open, empathetic communication.

Overall, the reviewed Philippine-based studies establish a consistent relationship between administrative practices, teacher satisfaction, and retention. However, most of these studies were conducted in urban or semi-urban areas. While previous studies have concentrated on urban or semi-urban divisions, the unique administrative and environmental dynamics of rural schools, such as Calatrava, remain underexplored. There remains limited evidence from rural public school districts such as Calatrava, where contextual factors may influence the dynamics of administrative support, teachers' professional contentment, and teacher retention.

Synthesis

This section synthesizes conceptual, foreign, and local literature on administrative support and its impact on teachers' professional contentment and retention, particularly in public elementary schools. Across studies, administrative support has consistently emerged as a key factor in enhancing teachers' motivation, well-being, and commitment.

Conceptual literature emphasizes that school leaders who provide guidance, balanced workloads, professional development, and recognition create environments where teachers feel valued and capable. Leadership practices that promote trust, collaboration, and support enhance resilience and psychological well-being, enabling sustained job satisfaction and effective performance.

Foreign studies have confirmed that empathetic communication, mentoring, participatory decision-making, and equitable task distribution reduce stress and burnout while strengthening teacher morale and retention. Administrators who invest in teacher growth and acknowledge contributions foster loyalty and long-term commitment among teachers.

Local Philippine studies reflect similar patterns, showing that mentoring, professional development, recognition, clear leadership direction, and fair workload management improve motivation, well-being, and belonging. Excessive workload and weak support contribute to dissatisfaction and burnout. Retention strengthens when leaders demonstrate fairness, empathy, and consistent support, although rural schools like those in Calatrava District I remain unexplored.

Overall, strong administrative support enhances teachers' satisfaction and retention, supported by key motivational and organizational theories, and contributes to sustainable school development aligned with United Nations SDG 4 and SDG 8.

Theoretical Framework

This investigation draws from Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, which explains how individuals are motivated to satisfy needs in a specific progression, beginning with basic physical needs and advancing toward self-actualization (Maslow, 1943). Within school settings, administrative support meets teachers' needs for security (through job stability), belonging (through collegial connections), esteem (through recognition), and self-actualization (through professional development). For example, when school administrators acknowledge a teacher's performance during faculty meetings and provide growth opportunities, the teacher feels recognized (esteem) and empowered to grow professionally (self-actualization). This theory connects with the findings of the study by showing that when teachers feel that their psychological needs are supported by school leadership, they are more likely to feel satisfied in their roles and choose to stay in the teaching profession.

Organizational Support Theory (OST) explains how teachers come to believe that their school values their work and cares for them (Eisenberger et al., 1986). These beliefs are not formed overnight; they grow gradually through everyday experiences. For instance, when teachers receive useful feedback, fair treatment, and practical help with their struggles, they start to feel that their school is on their side. Simple actions, such as providing the right teaching materials, reducing an extra load, or pairing them with a mentor can make teachers feel supported. OST suggests that when this happens, teachers are happier in their jobs and more likely to stay in them.

Social Exchange Theory (SET), introduced by Peter Michael Blau (1964), takes this idea further by examining the give-and-take in relationships. In schools, when administrators consistently support teachers through encouragement, professional growth, or fair workloads, teachers usually respond with loyalty, better performance, and commitment to their schools. SET also reminds us that these exchanges do not always look the same. The effect of support depends on the school's environment and culture; therefore, outcomes can vary from one place to another.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory focuses on two sets of influences. Motivators such as recognition and career development, bring satisfaction and make teachers feel fulfilled. Hygiene factors, such as clear rules and fair workload, may not make teachers happy, but they prevent frustration and burnout. This theory makes it clear that solving problems is insufficient. School leaders must also create opportunities that inspire teachers and provide them with reasons to grow (Herzberg et al., 1959).

When these four theoretical perspectives are combined, they all point to the same conclusion: administrative support is important. It shapes teachers' feelings about their work, their school, and decision to stay. For rural schools like Calatrava District I, where challenges are greater due to limited resources and teacher isolation, these theories help explain why leadership support is important. This study aims to better understand how school administrators can reduce stress, improve satisfaction, and strengthen teacher retention.

Conceptual Framework

This study, "Administrative Support and Its Effectiveness on Teachers' Professional Contentment and Retention, used the input-process-output (IPO) model as its guiding framework. The IPO model provides a systematic way of looking at how administrative support affects teachers' satisfaction and their willingness to remain in the school. Through this lens, the study seeks to show how the support given by administrators contributes to improving the overall work environment of teachers in Calatrava District I.

The input of the study comprised three key variables: (1) administrative support, (2) teachers' professional contentment, and (3) teacher retention. The first variable, administrative support, is viewed in terms of professional development, workload management, and stress-reduction strategies. Professional development refers to the opportunities provided to teachers for training, advanced learning, involvement in capacity- building activities, and receiving constructive feedback. Workload management focuses on fair task assignments, clear communication of responsibilities, and guidance from administrators that help teachers carry out their duties effectively. Stress-reduction measures include adjusting workloads during demanding periods, offering access to wellness or stress-management programs, acknowledging teachers' contributions, and creating policies that ease work-related pressure. The second variable, teachers' professional contentment, was assessed through their overall satisfaction, well-being, and motivation. This study examined how supported teachers feel in their roles, how positive they view their work experiences, and how motivated they are to continue performing well. The third variable, teacher retention, involved examining teachers' intention to remain in their positions and commitment to the school. Retention was shaped by the level of support they received and their overall workplace. These inputs were supported by four major theories: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, Organizational Support Theory, Social Exchange Theory, and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory. Together, these factors collectively explain how administrative practices influence teachers' experiences and decisions to remain in the profession.

The study involved administering a random survey questionnaire to 160 public elementary school teachers out of 262 elementary school teachers holding plantilla items in Calatrava District I. The instrument used of Likert scale items to gather information on the extent of administrative support, the level of professional contentment, and the degree of teacher retention. Each completed questionnaire was carefully reviewed for accuracy and completeness. The validated responses were encoded numerically and analyzed using SPSS version 27, following a quantitative descriptive-

correlational research design. This approach allows reliable examination of the relationships between variables.

The output of this research was the development of a Faculty Development Plan that addresses areas for improvement based on the survey results. This plan was designed to strengthen the aspects of administrative support that most significantly contribute to teachers' satisfaction and retention. Ultimately, the framework provides a data-driven basis for enhancing educational leadership practices, improving teacher well-being, and fostering long-term retention in Calatrava District I.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework: A Research Flow Model

Statement of the Problem

This study investigated the effect of administrative support on teachers' professional contentment and retention in Calatrava District I. This study aims to measure the level of administrative support provided by school administrators and examine its relationship with key indicators of teachers' professional contentment and retention.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of effectiveness of administrative support in terms of:
 - a. Availability of professional development opportunities
 - b. Workload management; and
 - c. Stress reduction interventions
2. What is the level of teachers' professional contentment, as indicated by the following:
 - a. Overall satisfaction;
 - b. Well-being; and

c. Motivation

3. What is the level of teacher retention in Calatrava District I in terms of:

a. Intention to stay; and

b. Commitment to the school?

4. Is there a significant relationship between administrative support and teachers' professional contentment?

5. Is there a significant relationship between administrative support and teacher retention?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following alternative hypotheses were proposed in this study:

H₁: There is a significant relationship between administrative support and teachers' professional contentment.

H₂: There is a significant relationship between administrative support and teacher retention.

Significance of the Study

This study benefited the following groups.

School Administrators. The results help school administrators understand the influence of their leadership and management approaches on teacher retention. The results guided administrators in formulating specific programs that improve teachers' contentment and reduce turnover.

Calatrava District I Public Elementary School Teachers. The findings helped teachers feel more valued and supported by identifying the administrative practices that most improved morale. Good working conditions among educators encourage a higher level of job satisfaction, a higher level of commitment, and a likelihood of staying in the profession.

Students. A satisfied and well-supported teaching workforce directly benefits students by ensuring that they receive continuous, high-quality education. When teachers experience strong administrative support, they are more motivated and engaged, resulting in improved classroom performance and a stable learning environment.

Parents. A stable and well-supported teaching workforce reassures parents that their children's education will not be disrupted by frequent staff change. When teachers feel content and supported, parents can have greater confidence that their children are receiving continuous and effective learning experiences.

Future Researchers. This study intends to provide references for future research on administrative support, teachers' professional contentment and their retention, which can guide further investigations aimed at improving education management and teacher well-being. Overall, this study contributes to improving teacher satisfaction and educational quality in Calatrava District I.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on the effectiveness of administrative support in shaping teachers' professional contentment and retention in Calatrava District I for the Academic Year 2025-2026. It specifically examined how professional development opportunities, workload management, and stress-reduction interventions influenced teachers' overall satisfaction, well-being, motivation, and intention to remain in teaching positions.

The independent variable is administrative support. On the other hand, the dependent variables are teachers' professional contentment and teacher retention.

Of the 22 public elementary schools in Calatrava District I, 160 teachers were selected as respondents using a stratified random sampling approach. Teacher respondents answered a validated self-made research questionnaire to provide data on administrative support, teachers' professional contentment, and retention. The gathered information was analyzed using a

quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) were used to summarize the data collected. On the other hand, inferential statistical tools like Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient were applied to interpret relationships among variables.

This study focused only on teachers in public elementary schools holding Plantilla items within Calatrava District I. It does not include teachers from other public or private schools outside the district or those from private or public high schools. In addition, factors such as salary and personal circumstances that may affect teachers' satisfaction and retention are beyond the main scope of this study. The study will also be based on self-reported data, which may reflect the individual perceptions and experiences.

The outcome of this study was proposed to guide the creation of a Faculty Development Plan that strengthens support for teachers, boosts their professional satisfaction, improves retention, and enhances the overall quality of education in the schools under Calatrava District I. This initiative also aligns with United Nations Sustainable Development Goals 4 and 8, providing useful insights for administrators and future researchers.

Definition of Terms

For a clear understanding and to avoid confusion regarding the terms used in this study, the following terms are operationally defined.

Administrative Support. Administrative support includes leadership approaches, policies, availability of professional development opportunities, workload management, and stress reduction interventions provided by school administrators in Calatrava District I, which influence teachers' professional contentment and retention.

Commitment to the School. Commitment to the school refers to teachers' sense of loyalty, responsibility, and dedication toward their current school, reflected in their willingness to actively contribute to school programs, support colleagues, and uphold the school's goals and values, as influenced by administrative support and professional contentment.

Intention to Stay. Intention to stay refers to teachers' willingness or decision to continue working in their current school assignment or within the district of Calatrava I for the coming years, as influenced by their job satisfaction and administrative support.

Motivation. Motivation refers to the level of enthusiasm and drive teachers must have to perform their duties effectively, pursue professional development, and remain committed to the teaching profession.

Overall Satisfaction. Overall satisfaction refers to the general level of contentment teachers feel towards their jobs, including their experiences with administrative support, work environment, and professional growth opportunities.

Professional Contentment. Professional contentment refers to the extent to which public elementary school teachers in Calatrava District I feel content, appreciated and motivated in their profession owing to administrative support and good working conditions.

Professional Development. Professional development refers to training programs, workshops, seminars, and other learning opportunities provided by schools or districts to enhance teachers' skills, knowledge, and professional growth.

Stress Reduction Interventions. Stress reduction interventions refer to the strategies, programs, or activities implemented by the school administration to help teachers manage work-related stress and maintain their overall well-being, such as counselling, wellness initiatives, recognition programs, and team-building activities.

Teacher Retention. Teacher retention is measured by the percentage of teachers who continue working and are committed to Calatrava District I, as influenced by the support they receive from school administrators.

Well-being. Well-being refers to teachers’ overall physical, emotional, and mental health, as influenced by their working conditions, support from administration, and work-life balance.

Workload Management. Workload Management refers to how teaching tasks, responsibilities, communication, and schedules are organized and distributed to ensure that teachers can perform their duties efficiently without excessive stress or burnout.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discussed the methodological aspects to be observed during the process, covering the research design, respondents, research instruments, reliability and validity, data gathering procedures, data analysis procedure, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study used a quantitative descriptive correlational research design. The descriptive component aimed to provide a detailed overview of the levels of administrative support, teacher professional contentment, and teacher retention, while the correlational component examined the relationships between administrative support and the two outcome variables. This design allowed the researcher to analyze patterns and associations within existing groups without manipulating any conditions. It is well-suited for studies that explore associations within existing groups (Creswell et al., 2018).

Respondents of the Study

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

RESPONDENTS	N	n	PERCENTAGE
ANI-E ES	8	5	3.05%
BAGACAY ES	8	5	3.05%
BANTAYANON ES	8	5	3.05%
BUENAVISTA ES	11	7	4.20%
CABUNGAHAN ES	8	5	3.05%
CALAPNUSAN ES	11	7	4.20%
C1CS	41	25	15.65%
CRUZ ES	7	4	2.67%
DELA ROSA ES	7	4	2.67%
DOLIS ES	15	9	5.73%
LAGA-AN ES	19	11	7.25%
LAGOC IS	8	5	3.05%
LALONG IS	8	5	3.05%
MAASLOB ES	7	4	2.67%
MALANOG ES	8	5	3.05%
MENCHACA ES	17	10	6.49%
PATUN-AN ES	15	9	5.73%
RMMES	13	8	4.96%
SAN BENITO IS	6	4	2.29%
SAN ISIDRO IS	16	10	6.11%
TELIM ES	8	5	3.05%
TIGBON ES	13	8	4.96%
TOTAL	262	160	100%

The respondents of this study consisted of 160 public elementary school teachers from the twenty-two (22) schools in Calatrava District I during the School Year 2025-2026. The teacher respondents were selected using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure representation from each school. In this method, every school served as a stratum, and the number of teacher respondents chosen from each school was based on the total teacher population per school.

From a total population of 262 teachers, 160 were selected as the sample size using proportional allocation, computed through Slovin’s formula with a 5% margin of error. This sampling method ensures that each teacher had an equal chance of being included in the study while maintaining balanced representation across all schools in Calatrava District I.

The distribution of respondents per school is presented in the table below. The selected sample size was considered sufficient to represent the target population while ensuring the accuracy, validity, and reliability of results.

Research Instrument

In assessing the effectiveness of administrative support on teachers’ professional contentment and retention, the main tool for gathering the data was a self-made questionnaire.

The instrument is composed of four main parts: (1) Profile of Respondents, (2) Administrative Support, (3) Teachers’ Professional Contentment, and (4) Teacher Retention. The first part focused on the profile of respondents, which gathered their personal information (name - optional, position, years in service, and school assignment). Next is the administrative support. This focused on teachers’ professional development opportunities, workload management, and stress reduction interventions. Then, the third part deals with teachers’ professional contentment. This measured the overall satisfaction, well-being, and motivation among the teachers at Calatrava District I. The last part centered on teacher retention, which assessed teachers’ intention to stay and commitment to the school.

The Likert scale allows participants to express the extent of their agreement with each statement. All items are rated on a Likert scale indicating the level of agreement:

Administrative Support

(Professional Development Opportunities, Workload Management, Stress Reduction Interventions)

Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High	Administrative support is highly effective.
4	3.41 – 4.20	High	Administrative support is effective.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	Administrative support is moderately effective but not consistent.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low	Administrative support is less effective.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	Administrative support is hardly effective.

Teachers’ Professional Contentment

(Overall Satisfaction, Well-Being, Motivation)

Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High	Teachers demonstrate very high contentment.
4	3.41 – 4.20	High	Teachers demonstrate high contentment.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	Teachers demonstrate moderate contentment.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low	Teachers demonstrate low contentment.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	Teachers demonstrate very low contentment.

Teacher Retention

(Intention to Stay, Commitment to the School)

Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very High	Teachers are very highly committed to remain in the school.
4	3.41 – 4.20	High	Teachers are highly committed to remain in the school.
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	Teachers show moderate commitment to remain; retention is evident to some extent.

2	1.81 – 2.60	Low	Teachers show low commitment to remain in the school.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low	Teachers show very low commitment to remain in the school.

Reliability and Validity of the Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was a self-made questionnaire, carefully constructed based on study’s theoretical framework to ensure alignment with the research objectives. The items were written in clear and concise language, appropriate to the local school context, and designed to measure the intended constructs accurately.

Validity was established through expert evaluation. Three specialists in education and school leadership meticulously reviewed each item to assess its relevance, clarity, and appropriateness for measuring the variables. The Good and Scates rating system was employed as the evaluation standard, providing a structured framework for experts to rate each item. Expert feedback confirmed that the questionnaire comprehensively covered all study variables. The instrument achieved an overall validity rating of 5 (excellent), indicating that all items were highly suitable for research purposes.

The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha to assess internal consistency. The validated questionnaire, consisting of 40 items, was pilot-tested with 30 teachers, 15 from Tandang Sora Elementary School and 15 from the School of the Future. The instrument yielded a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.986, demonstrating excellent reliability and a very high level of consistency among the items. This indicates that the questionnaire reliably measures the intended constructs and that the items function cohesively to assess the variables being studied.

Overall, the results of both expert validation and reliability testing confirmed that the instrument was valid and highly reliable, making it suitable for the main study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Office of Negros Occidental and the school heads by sending a formal letter of request to conduct the study. Copies of the letter were also furnished to the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) and the District Research Coordinator.

Upon approval, data were collected over a week in January 2026. Each participant received a letter detailing the purpose and scope of the study, along with an informed consent form. After providing consent, teachers were asked to complete the questionnaire in person. Given the large number of respondents across 22 schools, the researcher coordinated with school heads and administrative officers to assist in distributing and collecting the questionnaires. This collaboration ensured that the data collection process was efficient, accurate, and did not disrupt the school’s operations.

All respondents’ identities and responses were kept confidential, and no personal information was publicly disclosed.

Data Analysis Procedure

After gathering all the completed research questionnaires, each was carefully reviewed to ensure that the answers were complete and clearly indicated. Once verified, the data was organized and encoded into a spreadsheet in preparation for analysis. The responses on the Likert scale were converted into numerical values to facilitate analysis.

Descriptive statistics, such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were computed manually to summarize the data and determine the levels of administrative support, teachers’ professional contentment, and teacher retention. For inferential analysis, the data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27, specifically to examine the relationships among variables using Pearson’s Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Statistical Treatment

The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design consists of two main components: descriptive and correlational component. The descriptive component summarized and presented the data, providing a clear overview of the levels of administrative support, teachers' professional contentment, and teacher retention. The correlational component examined relationships among variables to determine how administrative support influences teacher outcomes.

To address Research Questions 1, 2, and 3, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used.

Frequency (f) was used to determine the number of respondents in each item.

Percentage (P) was calculated to determine the proportion of respondents in each item.

Mean (M) was calculated to determine the levels of administrative support, teachers' professional contentment, and teacher retention.

Standard Deviation (SD) was computed to assess the consistency of responses across variables.

To answer Research Questions 4 and 5, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was applied to examine the strength and direction of relationships among the variables. The level of significance was set at 0.05. The obtained p-value indicates whether the relationship is statistically significant.

This combination of descriptive and correlational analyses ensured that the study systematically assessed both the levels and interrelationships of the key variables. The results from these statistical procedures guided the interpretation and conclusions of the study, providing evidence-based insights into the effectiveness of administrative support on teacher outcomes.

Ethical Considerations

This study was submitted to the Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos, Inc. Graduate School for assessment as required by the institution. To ensure rigor, trustworthiness, and ethical conduct, the following measures were observed:

Permission was secured from the Schools Division Office and the school heads to allow the researcher to conduct the surveys among the teachers. Copies of the request letters were also furnished to the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) and the District Research Coordinator for proper monitoring.

Free and informed consent forms were distributed to all participants. They were informed of their right to withdraw from the survey at any time, without prejudice or coercion, and were not required to provide a reason for withdrawing. Participants' identities were treated with the utmost confidentiality, and they were given the opportunity to elaborate on or modify their responses, if needed.

The researcher ensured that the contributions of each participant were fairly represented in the study and took precautions against unauthorized access, maintaining data integrity in accordance with institutional and regulatory requirements. All data were reported only in the aggregate and were securely stored for five (5) years following the completion of the study. After this period, the data will be safely disposed of using paper shredder, with the disposal process properly documented.

These measures guarantee transparency, accountability, and evidence that ethical issues were thoroughly considered and appropriately addressed throughout the research.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the study entitled "Administrative Support and Its Effectiveness on Teachers' Professional Contentment and Retention." The findings were based on data gathered from 160 Elementary Public School Teachers in Calatrava District I, using a

validated self-made questionnaire. The results were presented according to the major variables of the study: Administrative Support, Teachers’ Professional Contentment and Retention. The discussion was supported by recent and relevant literature.

Administrative Support

Administrative support was examined in terms of professional development opportunities, workload management, and stress-reduction interventions.

Administrative Support in Terms of Professional Development Opportunities

Table 2A. Administrative Support in Terms of Professional Development Opportunities

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Administrators encourage participation in professional development activities.	112	39	9	0	0	160	100	4.64	0.58	Very High
Administrators show that professional development is valued.	108	44	8	0	0	160	100	4.62	0.58	Very High
Feedback from administrators help me improve my teaching performance.	107	45	8	0	0	160	100	4.62	0.58	Very High
Administrators provide training opportunities that enhance my professional growth.	103	50	7	0	0	160	100	4.60	0.57	Very High
The school supports my pursuit of higher learning.	96	54	8	1	1	160	100	4.52	0.68	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.60	0.60	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 2A showed that administrative support in terms of professional development opportunities was perceived at a Very High level, with an overall mean of 4.60 (SD = 0.60). This indicates that administrative support for professional development opportunities was highly effective.

The highest-rated indicator, “Administrators encourage participation in professional development activities” (M = 4.64, Very High), reflects strong leadership support for continuous learning. Closely related items, such as “Administrators show that professional development is valued” and “Feedback from administrators help me improve my teaching performance” (both M = 4.62, Very High), indicate that administrators actively promote teacher growth, provide guidance, and reinforce the importance of professional learning. Importantly, “Administrators provide training opportunities that enhance my professional growth” (M =4.60, Very High), showed that teachers perceived concrete training programs as readily available. Even the lowest-rated indicator, “The school supports my pursuit of higher learning” (M = 4.52), remains within the Very High category, indicating consistent institutional support for teachers’ professional advancement.

These results were consistent with Northouse (2022), who emphasized that effective leadership involves developing followers' skills and competencies to enhance both individual and organizational performance. Professional development also served as a critical job resource, strengthening teachers' coping capacity and reducing turnover intentions (Collie, 2023). Moreover, sustained institutional support for growth contributes to improved teacher resilience and long-term career commitment (Davis & Park, 2025)

In a broader context, the strong emphasis on professional development aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), which highlights the importance of skills development, productive employment, and decent working conditions. By investing in continuous professional growth, school administrators contribute to motivating, sustainable, and dignified work environments in the education sector (United Nations, 2024).

Administrative Support in Terms of Workload Management

Table 2B. Administrative Support in Terms of Workload Management

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Administrators ensure that my workload is fair.	105	44	10	1	0	160	100	4.58	0.64	Very High
Administrative guidance helps me manage my work effectively.	99	51	8	2	0	160	100	4.54	0.65	Very High
Administrators communicate tasks clearly.	98	47	13	1	1	160	100	4.50	0.72	Very High
Raise concerns about workload without hesitation.	97	47	14	1	1	160	100	4.49	0.73	Very High
Administrators provide timely instructions when tasks change.	94	50	13	2	1	160	100	4.46	0.75	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.51	0.70	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 2B showed that administrative support in terms of workload management was perceived at a Very High level, with an overall mean of 4.51 (SD = 0.70). This indicates that administrative support for workload management was highly effective.

The highest-rated indicator, "Administrators ensure that my workload is fair" (M = 4.58, Very High), reflects equitable distribution of responsibilities. Closely related items, such as "Administrative guidance helps me manage my work effectively" (M = 4.54, Very High), "Administrators communicate tasks clearly" (M = 4.50, Very High), and "Raise concerns about workload without hesitation" (M = 4.49, Very High), indicate that administrators provide clarity, guidance, and openness, enabling teachers to manage their responsibilities efficiently. Even the lowest-rated item "Administrators provide timely instructions when tasks change" (M = 4.46), remains within the Very High category, suggesting consistent and highly effective administrators support for workload management.

These findings were consistent with Creagh (2025), who emphasized that unmanaged workloads and work intensification are major contributors to teacher stress, burnout, and time poverty. The results are further reinforced by the Department of Education (DepEd) Order No. 002., s. 2024, which mandates the immediate removal of non-teaching administrative tasks from public school teachers, protecting instructional time and reducing unnecessary workload burdens (Department of Education, 2024). Clear communication and responsive leadership also enhance collaborative

management and reduce role overload (Komari et al., 2024), while manageable workloads have been shown to improve teaching performance and reduce burnout (Magtalas, 2024).

In broader context, the administrators' support for workload management aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), which emphasized productive employment, safe and fair working conditions, and the protection of workers' time and well-being (United Nations, 2024). By implementing fair and policy-aligned workload practices, school leaders not only improved teacher well-being and performance but also contributed to sustainable and dignified working conditions in the education sector.

Administrative Support in Terms of Stress Reduction Interventions

Table 2C. Administrative Support in Terms of Stress Reduction Interventions

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Administrative policies include strategies that ease workplace stress.	82	62	15	1	0	160	100	4.41	0.68	Very High
Recognition from administrators reduces the stress I experience at work.	82	60	16	2	0	160	100	4.39	0.72	Very High
Teachers are given opportunities to openly discuss stress-related concerns with administrators.	81	62	14	2	1	160	100	4.39	0.75	Very High
Administrators adjust workloads when teachers experience high levels of stress at work.	82	60	14	3	1	160	100	4.37	0.77	Very High
The school provides access to stress management services for teachers.	73	60	21	4	2	160	100	4.24	0.86	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.36	0.76	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 2C indicates that administrative support for stress reduction interventions was perceived at a Very High level, with an overall mean of 4.36 (SD = 0.76). This indicates that administrative support for stress management was highly effective.

The highest-rated item, “Administrative policies include strategies that ease workplace stress” (M = 4.41, Very High), indicates that stress management is embedded in school policies. Closely related items, such as “Recognition from administrators reduces the stress at work” (M = 4.39, Very High) and “Teachers are given opportunities to openly discuss stress-related concerns with administrators” (M = 4.39, Very High), highlight the importance of emotional, psychological, and communicative support in reducing teachers' stress. Similarly, “Administrators adjust workloads when teachers experience high levels of stress at work” (M = 4.37, Very High), reflects responsive leadership that prioritizes teacher well-being. Even the lowest-rated item, “The school provides access to stress management services for teachers” (M = 4.24, Very High), indicating that support mechanisms were generally present, though accessibility or visibility may vary.

These findings were consistent with Beames et al. (2023), who reported that organizational level interventions including supportive leadership, recognition, and open communication effectively reduce stress and professional burnout. Recognition and opportunities for dialogue emphasize the role of emotionally responsive leadership, which align with Zheng et al. (2024), who found that

gratitude and acknowledgement from leaders significantly enhance teachers’ psychological well-being and work engagement.

Furthermore, Agpayong et al. (2023) highlighted that systematic stress reduction strategies are more sustainable and impactful than individual-focused interventions alone.

In a broader context, administrative support for stress reduction aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education), which emphasizes the need for safe, supportive, and healthy learning environments to ensure effective teaching and learning outcomes (United Nations, 2024). By prioritizing stress management and mental health support, administrators helped maintain teachers’ well-being, engagement, and capacity to deliver high-quality education.

Administrative Support in Terms of its Key Dimensions

Table 2D. Administrative Support in Terms of its Key Dimensions

Key Dimensions	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Professional Development Opportunities	4.60	0.60	Very High
Workload Management	4.51	0.70	Very High
Stress Reduction Interventions	4.36	0.76	Very High
Overall	4.49	0.69	Very High

Note. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 2D showed that administrative support across its key dimensions in Calatrava District I perceived at a Very High level (M = 4.49, SD = 0.69). This indicates highly effective support for teachers’ professional functioning and well-being.

Among the dimensions, *Professional Development Opportunities* received the highest rating (M = 4.60), followed by *Workload Management* (M = 4.51) and *Stress Reduction Interventions* (M = 4.36), all reflecting strong leadership support in fostering growth, fair workload distribution, clear guidance, responsive leadership and teacher well-being.

These findings were consistent with Bagdžiūnienė et al. (2022), who reported that supportive leadership enhances teachers’ coping strategies and resilience. Moreover, administrative support has been shown to influence long-term outcomes, including teacher retention and organizational commitment (Ubal, 2025) and sustained teacher satisfaction through structured support systems and professional development opportunities (Shaoan, 2025).

Building on the connections highlighted in the previous dimensions (Tables 2A – 2C) aligned with United Nations SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 8 (Decent Work Economic Growth), promoting effective teaching, well-being, and sustainable employment (United Nations, 2024). Policies such as DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024 further support workload management by protecting instructional time and reducing administrative burdens, reinforcing inclusive and productive school environments (Relativo, 2024).

Teachers’ Professional Contentment

Teachers’ Professional Contentment was examined in terms of overall satisfaction, well-being and motivation.

Teachers’ Professional Contentment in Terms of Overall Satisfaction

Table 3A. Teachers’ Professional Contentment in Terms of Overall Satisfaction

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
I am satisfied with the professional development	105	46	8	1	0	160	100	4.59	0.62	Very High

opportunities available to me.										
I am satisfied with how my administrators distribute my workload fairly.	101	49	9	1	0	160	100	4.56	0.63	Very High
Overall, I am satisfied with the support provided by the school leadership.	100	43	15	1	1	160	100	4.51	0.74	Very High
I am satisfied with the feedback I received from my administrators.	99	46	13	1	1	160	100	4.50	0.72	Very High
I am satisfied with the recognition I receive from administrators.	97	45	16	1	1	160	100	4.47	0.75	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.53	0.69	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 3A showed that teachers' professional contentment in terms of overall satisfaction was perceived at a Very High level ($M = 4.53$, $SD = 0.69$). This indicates that teachers demonstrated very high contentment with their professional experiences.

The highest-rated item, *I am satisfied with the professional development opportunities available to me* ($M = 4.59$, Very High), indicates that access to learning and growth opportunities was a major contributor to satisfaction. Closely related items, such as *"Satisfaction with fair workload distribution"* ($M = 4.56$, Very High), *"Support from school leadership"* ($M = 4.51$, Very High), and *"I am satisfied with the feedback I received from my administrators"* ($M = 4.50$, Very High), further reflect teachers' appreciation for equitable work allocations, consistent administrative support, and constructive guidance. Even the lowest-rated item, *"Satisfaction with recognition from administrators"* ($M = 4.47$, Very High), indicates that teachers generally feel valued and acknowledged.

These findings aligned with Sebulen and Jimenez (2024), who highlighted that transformational leadership and strong administrative support enhanced teacher job satisfaction. Similarly, Gilbert (2023) found that perceived administrative support directly influences teachers' affective organizational commitment and satisfaction. In addition, Tria (2023) emphasized that professional support, fair workload, and recognition were central determinants of teacher job satisfaction. Overall, these results suggest that administrative practices fostering professional growth, fair workload, and recognition effectively promote teachers' overall satisfaction.

Teachers' Professional Contentment in Terms of Well-being

Table 3B. Teachers' Professional Contentment in Terms of Well-being

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
My well-being improves when administrators adjust workloads during stressful times.	89	62	9	0	0	160	100	4.50	0.60	Very High
My well-being improves when administrative support helps me balance work and personal life.	91	56	13	0	0	160	100	4.49	0.64	Very High
Recognition from administrators contributes to	83	62	14	1	0	160	100	4.42	0.68	Very High

my emotional well-being.										
My well-being is supported when I can openly discuss stress-related concerns with administrators.	85	56	18	1	0	160	100	4.41	0.71	Very High
My well-being improves because the school provides stress management programs.	80	54	21	5	0	160	100	4.31	0.81	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.43	0.69	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 3B showed that teachers' professional contentment in terms of well-being was perceived at a Very High level (M = 4.43, SD = 0.69). This indicates that teachers demonstrated very high contentment within their professional environment.

The highest-rated items, *'My well-being improves when administrators adjust workloads during stressful times'* (M = 4.50, Very High) and *'My well-being improves when administrative support helps me balance work and personal life'* (M = 4.49, Very High), indicate that workload flexibility and support for work-life balance positively influence teachers' mental and emotional health. Closely related items, such as *'Recognition from administrators contributes to my emotional well-being'* (M = 4.42, Very High) and *'My well-being is supported when I can openly discuss stress-related concerns with administrators'* (M = 4.41, Very High), further highlighted the importance of emotional and psychological support. Even the lowest-rated item, *'My well-being improves because the school provides stress management programs'* (M = 4.31, Very High), showed that such interventions were generally present and appreciated by teachers.

These results were consistent with Arbia et al. (2023), who reported that administrative support, emotional recognition, and workload management were key factors in reducing teacher stress and improving well-being. Pan et al. (2023) emphasized that preparedness, autonomy, and organizational support predict higher teacher well-being. In line with Magalong and Torreon (2021) and the DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024, workload adjustments and the removal of non-teaching administrative tasks allowed teachers to maintain balance and reduce stress. These practices ensured teachers remain psychologically supported and able to perform effectively.

Teachers' Professional Contentment in Terms of Motivation

Table 3C. Teachers' Professional Contentment in Terms of Motivation

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
I am motivated to perform well when administrators provide opportunities for professional growth.	111	39	9	1	0	160	100	4.63	0.62	Very High
My motivation increases when my efforts are recognized by administrators.	107	47	5	1	0	160	100	4.63	0.58	Very High
Administrative support motivates me to improve my teaching performance.	109	40	10	1	0	160	100	4.61	0.63	Very High
I am motivated when encouraged to take part in professional development activities.	100	52	7	1	0	160	100	4.57	0.61	Very High

I am motivated to remain committed to my work when administrators respond promptly to task changes.	100	50	8	2	0	160	100	4.55	0.65	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.60	0.62	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 3C showed that teachers' motivation was perceived at a Very High level ($M = 4.60$, $SD = 0.62$). This indicates that teachers demonstrated very high contentment in their professional roles.

The highest-rated indicators, "I am motivated to perform well when administrators provide opportunities for professional growth" ($M = 4.63$, Very High) and "My motivation increases when my efforts are recognized by administrators" ($M = 4.63$, Very High), indicated that both skill development and acknowledgment were strong motivators. Closely related items, such as "Administrative support motivates me to improve my teaching performance" ($M = 4.61$, Very High), "I am motivated when encouraged to take part in professional development activities" ($m = 4.57$, Very High), and "I am motivated to remain committed to my work when administrators respond promptly to task changes" ($M = 4.55$, Very High), further indicated that leadership practices enhanced teachers' engagement, commitment, and overall performance.

These findings were supported by Tirana et al. (2023), who identified recognition, professional growth, and supportive leadership as major factors influencing teacher motivation. Sebulen and Juimenez (2024) also emphasized that transformational leadership behaviors, such as promoting autonomy and skill development, enhanced motivation and engagement. Additionally, Garcia et al. (2023) noted that supportive leadership mitigates technostress and strengthens teachers' capacity to performed effectively.

Collectively, these results underscore that teacher motivation was closely linked to administrative support: professional development opportunities, workload management, and stress reduction intervention.

Teachers' Professional Contentment in Terms of its Key Dimensions

Table 3D. Teachers' Professional Contentment in Terms of its Key Dimensions

Key Dimensions	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Motivation	4.60	0.62	Very High
Overall Satisfaction	4.53	0.69	Very High
Well-being	4.43	0.69	Very High
Overall	4.52	0.67	Very High

Note. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 3D showed that teachers' professional contentment across its key dimensions in Calatrava District I was perceived at a Very High level ($M = 4.49$, $SD = 0.69$). This indicates that teachers demonstrate very high contentment in their professional roles, reflecting strong engagement, satisfaction, and well-being.

Among the dimensions, *Motivation* received the highest rating ($M = 4.60$), followed by *Overall Satisfaction* ($M = 4.53$) and *Well-being* ($M = 4.43$), reflecting that teachers are highly motivated, satisfied with their professional experiences, and maintain strong mental and emotional health.

These findings were consistent with research demonstrating that a positive organizational climate and fulfillment of psychological needs significantly predict teacher well-being (Harrison et al., 2024), and that a supportive working environment enhances job satisfaction and psychological well-being (Chen et al., 2024). Furthermore, a healthy and positive school climate positively influences both teacher motivation and job satisfaction, with motivation often acting as a mediator in this relationship (Erdem & Kocyigit, 2025). This supports the interpretation that the high motivation rating reflects not only individual teacher factors but also the influence of a supportive organizational environment, where recognition, professional growth opportunities, and responsive leadership enhance both satisfaction and engagement (Li et al., 2025).

Building on the patterns observed across the key dimensions of professional contentment (Tables 3A – 3C), teachers in Calatrava District I demonstrated very high engagement, satisfaction, and well-being in their professional roles. These high levels of professional contentment collectively aligned with United Nations SDG 4 and SDG 8, promoting quality education, professional growth, and sustainable employment in schools (United Nations, 2024). Collectively, these results indicate that administrative support through professional development opportunities, workload management, and stress reduction interventions fosters teachers’ satisfaction, motivation, and well-being by creating a supportive organizational environment, contributing to sustainable and productive school contexts.

Teacher Retention

Teacher retention was examined in terms of intention to stay and commitment to the school.

Teacher Retention in Terms of Intention to Stay

Table 4A. Retention in Terms of Intention to Stay

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
I intend to continue teaching at Calatrava District I for the next school year.	128	24	7	1	0	160	100	4.74	0.56	Very High
I see myself teaching at Calatrava District I for many more years.	125	22	11	2	0	160	100	4.69	0.65	Very High
I prefer to stay in this school rather than transfer to another.	115	28	13	4	0	160	100	4.59	0.74	Very High
I plan to remain in this school for at least the next three years.	110	29	18	2	1	160	100	4.53	0.79	Very High
I am committed to staying in this school as long as possible.	106	34	16	4	0	160	100	4.51	0.77	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.61	0.70	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 4A showed that teachers’ intention to stay was perceived at a Very High level, with an overall mean of 4.61 (SD = 0.70). This indicates that teachers were very highly committed to remain in their school.

The highest-rated item, “*I intend to continue teaching in Calatrava District I for the next school year*” (M = 4.74, Very High), reflects strong short-term retention. Closely related items, such as “*I see myself teaching at Calatrava District I for many more years*” (M = 4.69, Very High), “*I prefer*

to stay in this school rather than transfer to another” (M = 4.69, Very High), and “I plan to remain in this school for at least the next three years” (M = 4.53, Very High), demonstrated long-term commitment and dedication to the school. Even the lowest-rated item, “I am committed to staying in this school as long as possible” (M = 4.51, Very High), indicated stable attachment and strong retention intentions among teachers.

These findings were consistent with Collie (2023), who reported that teachers with strong job resources, supportive leadership, and manageable workloads exhibited lower turnover intentions. Similarly, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2023) emphasized that shared goals and psychological need satisfaction, and organizational support strengthened teachers’ motivation to remain in their roles. In the Philippine context, teacher shortages were a growing concern, with 38,463 fewer public school teachers in 2023 compared to 2022 (Commission on Audit, 2024), highlighting the importance of retention strategies. Administrative support, recognition of teachers’ efforts, and manageable workloads including the removal of non-teaching tasks (DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024) promote decent work conditions and sustained employment, directly supporting United Nations SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) (United Nations, 2024).

Teacher Retention in Terms of Commitment to the School

Table 4B. Retention in Terms of Commitment to the School

Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	f	%	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
I value my professional relationship within this school.	132	26	2	0	0	160	100	4.81	0.42	Very High
I have strong sense of belonging in this school.	120	35	4	1	0	160	100	4.71	0.54	Very High
I actively participate in school activities beyond my teaching duties.	117	40	3	0	0	160	100	4.71	0.49	Very High
I take pride in being part of this school community because of administrators support.	116	38	6	0	0	160	100	4.69	0.54	Very High
I take personal responsibility for the success of the school.	115	39	5	1	0	160	100	4.67	0.57	Very High
Overall						160	100	4.72	0.51	Very High

Note. SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree; f = frequency, % = percent. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 4B showed that teachers’ commitment to the school, in terms of length of service, was perceived at a Very High level (M = 4.72, SD = 0.51). This indicates that teachers were very highly committed to remain in the school over the long term.

The highest-rated item, “I value my professional relationship within this school” (M = 4.81, Very High), underscores the importance of collegiality in fostering loyalty. Closely related items, such as “I have a strong sense of belonging in this school” (M 4.71, Very High) and “I actively participate in school activities beyond my teaching duties” (M = 4.71, Very High), reflect teachers’ engagement with the school community.

Other items, including “I take pride in being part of this school community because of administrators support” (M = 4.69, Very High) and “I take personal responsibility for the success of the school” (M = 4.67, Very High), demonstrate strong professional and emotional attachment to the school.

These results were supported by Engle et al. (2024) and Zhan et al. (2023), who found that teacher retention was positively influenced by leadership support, a sense of belonging, and alignment with school values. Ramirez and Capili (2024) also noted that leadership style and proactive support measures directly impact teachers' willingness to remain in a school. National initiatives, such as DepEd's hiring over 7,000 administrative support staff to ease teacher workload (Manila Bulletin, 2025), further sustained engagement and commitment by reducing stress and enabling teachers to focus on instruction. By cultivating such an environment, administrators create safe, motivating, and sustainable workplaces, directly supporting United Nations SDG 4 (Quality Education), which emphasizes well-supported teachers as essential for effective teaching and high-quality learning outcomes (United Nations, 2024).

Teacher Retention in Terms of its Key Dimensions

Table 4C. Teacher Retention in Terms of its Key Dimensions

Key Dimensions	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Rating
Commitment to the School	4.72	0.51	Very High
Intention to Stay	4.61	0.70	Very High
Overall	4.67	0.61	Very High

Note. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Mean scores correspond to the descriptive rating as follows: 4.21-5.00 (Very High), 3.41-4.20 (High), 2.61-3.40 (Moderate), 1.81-2.60 (Low), and 1.00-1.80 (Very Low).

Table 4C showed that teacher retention across its key dimensions in Calatrava District I was perceived at a Very High level ($M = 4.67$, $SD = 0.61$). This indicates that teachers were very highly committed to remain in the school, reflecting strong intention to stay and a solid commitment to the school community.

Among the dimensions, *Commitment to the School* received the highest rating ($M = 4.71$, Very High), followed by *Intention to Stay* ($M = 4.61$, Very High), indicating that teachers were deeply connected to their school community and plan to continue their service there.

These results were in line with findings that job satisfaction and a strong organizational climate including supportive leadership and collegial relationship are associated with higher retention and commitment (Domnena et al., 2024). A supportive school environment characterized by collegial collaboration and positive leadership not only enhances teachers' sense of belonging but also strengthens their willingness to remain in the profession (Anog et al., 2024). Professional commitment was positively related to a supportive work climate, with more committed teachers tending to exhibit higher levels of job satisfaction and collaboration (Mangarin & Macalde, 2024).

In a broader context, very high levels of teacher retention aligned with United Nations Sustainable Development 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), which emphasize the importance of equitable access to quality education and decent work conditions that support teacher stability and well-being (United Nations, 2024).

Administrative Support and Teachers' Professional Contentment

Teachers' professional contentment was examined in relation to the level of effectiveness of administrative support.

Relationship between Administrative Support and Teachers' Professional Contentment

Table 5. Relationship Between Administrative Support and Teachers' Professional Contentment

Variables Correlated	r	p-value	n	Interpretation
Administrative Support and Teachers' Professional Contentment	0.986	0.001	160	Very Strong Positive Correlation; Significant

Note. $N = 160$. Level of significance: $\alpha = 0.05$. Degrees of freedom: $df = N - 2 = 158$. R = Pearson correlation coefficient; p = probability value; n = number of respondents. Decision rule: if $p \leq 0.05$ = significant (reject H_0); if $p > 0.05$ = not significant (fail to reject H_0). Strength of relationship

(r): 0.00 – 0.19 = very weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = strong, 0.80 – 1.00 very strong.

Table 5 results showed a Very Strong Positive Correlation between administrative support and teachers’ professional contentment, which was statistically significant ($r = 0.986$, $p = 0.001$, $n = 160$). Since the p-value was less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that as the level of administrative support increases, teachers’ professional contentment also increases.

The finding was supported by Tosun and Bostanci (2024), who reported that stronger administrative support enhances teacher leadership, organizational engagement, and motivation. Similarly, Cervellione et al. (2025) emphasized that interventions targeting emotional regulation and reflective capacities improved teachers’ well-being, motivation and professional satisfaction. Practices such as equitable workload distribution and transparent communication further reduced work-related stress and foster a supportive environment, thereby contributing to overall teacher satisfaction and motivation (Tran et al., 2023). Collectively, administrative support is crucial for employees’ satisfaction, as it significantly enhances job satisfaction, which in turn improves employees’ motivation and their ability to achieve work objectives (Armstrong-Stassen, 2020).

Administrative Support and Teachers Retention

Teacher retention was examined in relation to the level of effectiveness of administrative support.

Relationship between Administrative Support and Teacher Retention

Table 6. Relationship Between Administrative Support and Teacher Retention

Variables Correlated	r	p-value	n	Interpretation
Administrative Support and Teacher Retention	0.960	0.009	160	Very Strong Positive Correlation; Significant

Note. N = 160. Level of significance: $\alpha = 0.05$. Degrees of freedom: $df = N - 2 = 158$. R = Pearson correlation coefficient; p = probability value; n = number of respondents. Decision rule: if $p \leq 0.05$ = significant (reject H_0); if $p > 0.05$ = not significant (fail to reject H_0). Strength of relationship (r): 0.00 – 0.19 = very weak, 0.20 – 0.39 = weak, 0.40 – 0.59 = moderate, 0.60 – 0.79 = strong, 0.80 – 1.00 very strong.

Table 6 results showed a Very Strong Positive Correlation between administrative support and teacher retention, which was statistically significant ($r = 0.960$, $p = 0.009$, $n = 160$). Since the p-value was less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that higher levels of administrative support were associated with higher teacher retention, suggesting that supportive administration plays a crucial role in encouraging teachers to remain in their positions.

This finding aligns with Jun et al., (2023), who reported that authentic leadership was associated with lower employee turnover intention by building trust and enhancing perceived supervisor support. Arnold and Rahimi (2025) emphasized that favorable working conditions combined with supportive leadership reduce teachers’ intentions to leave. Espira and Valle (2025) demonstrated that clear guidance and emotional encouragement from school leaders strengthen teachers’ morale and sense of belonging, supporting their decision to stay. Rafols and Pedroso (2025) found that administrative support practices in rural schools are linked with higher teacher retention, highlighting the importance of leadership styles that value and support educators.

Theoretical Discussion

The findings of this study were supported and explained by established organizational and motivational theories.

Administrative support in Calatrava District I ($M = 4.49$) aligned with Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs Theory and Organizational Support Theory, as professional development opportunities, fair

workload management, and stress reduction interventions meet teachers' psychological and growth needs while signaling that the school values their well-being.

Teachers' professional contentment ($M = 4.52$) was understood through Herzberg's Two Factor Theory, where motivators such as recognition, and opportunities for growth, along with hygiene factors like workload fairness and stress reduction, collectively enhanced satisfaction and engagement.

Finally, teacher retention ($M = 4.67$) reflects principles of Social Exchange Theory, whereby teachers reciprocate strong administrative support with loyalty and long-term commitment to their schools.

Collectively, these theories helped explained why highly effective administrative support strengthens teachers' overall satisfaction, motivation, well-being, and retention in the district.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the study on administrative support and its effectiveness on teachers' professional contentment and retention in Calatrava District I.

Summary of Findings

The study revealed that the **administrative support** in Calatrava District I was rated "Very High" with an overall mean of 4.49. Among the indicators, professional development opportunities received the highest score ($M = 4.60$), followed by workload management ($M = 4.51$) and stress reduction interventions ($M = 4.36$). This indicates that administrative support in the district is highly effective across all measured areas.

Similarly, **teachers' professional contentment** in Calatrava District I was rated as "Very High" with an overall mean of 4.52. Among the indicators, motivation received the highest score ($M = 4.60$), followed by overall satisfaction ($M = 4.53$) and well-being ($M = 4.43$), indicating that teachers in the district demonstrated very high contentment across all measured areas.

Likewise, **teacher retention** in Calatrava District I was rated as "Very High" with an overall mean of 4.67. Among the indicators, commitment to the school received the highest score ($M = 4.72$), followed by intention to stay ($M = 4.61$), indicating that teachers in the district are very highly committed to remain in their school.

In addition, **the relationship between administrative support and teachers' professional contentment** revealed a statistically significant, with a very strong positive correlation observed ($r = 0.986$, $p = 0.001$). This indicates that higher administrative support was strongly associated with greater teachers' professional contentment.

Finally, **the relationship between administrative support and teacher retention** revealed a statistically significant, with a Very Strong Positive Correlation observed **teacher retention** showed ($r = 0.960$, $p = 0.009$). This indicates that higher administrative support was strongly associated with greater teacher retention.

Conclusion

In view of foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

- 1. Administrative Support:** Administrative support in the Calatrava District I was highly effective, particularly in providing professional development opportunities, managing workloads, and implementing stress reduction interventions. This concludes that teachers received strong support from school administrators across key areas of their work. School administrators should

continue to prioritize these practices to sustain teacher satisfaction, engagement, and overall performance.

- 2. Teachers' Professional Contentment:** Teachers in Calatrava District I demonstrated very high contentment, with motivation, overall satisfaction, and well-being being the highest-rated indicators. This shows that effective administrative support contributes positively to teachers' satisfaction, engagement, and overall sense of well-being. Policies and programs that enhance administrative support can further strengthen teachers' professional contentment and well-being.
- 3. Teacher Retention:** Teacher retention in the Calatrava District I was very high, reflected by strong commitment to their schools and a high intention to continue teaching. This indicates that supportive administrative practices help maintain teacher stability and reduce turnover. Maintaining and improving supportive practices can help school retain experienced teachers, ensuring continuity and stability in education quality.
- 4. Relationship between Administrative Support and Teachers' Professional Contentment:** There was a significant and Very Strong Positive Correlation between administrative support and teachers' professional contentment in Calatrava District I. This confirmed that increased administrative support directly enhances teachers' satisfaction, motivation and well-being. School leaders should recognize the critical role of administrative support in fostering teacher engagement and prioritize interventions that strengthen these areas.
- 5. Relationship between Administrative Support and Teacher Retention:** There was a significant and Very Strong Positive Correlation between administrative support and teacher retention in Calatrava District I. This demonstrates that supportive administrative practices encouraged teachers to remain committed to their schools and careers in the district. Strengthening administrative support can be a strategic approach to improved teacher retention and reduce turnover, contributing to a stable and effective teaching workforce.

Therefore, these findings were particularly significant for rural schools, particularly Calatrava District I, where limited resources and administrative challenges often affect teacher satisfaction and retention. The results also emphasized the importance of recent DepEd policies, such as the removal of non-teaching administrative tasks, which helped improved teacher well-being and productivity, and overall professional experiences. Moreover, the study aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals: SDG 4 (Quality Education), as well-supported teachers can deliver high-quality instruction, respond to diverse learning needs, and ensure all students have access to inclusive and equitable education; and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), as safe, motivating, and respectful work environments enhance teacher satisfaction, retention, and long-term commitment to their schools. Finally, the findings of this study guided the development of a Faculty Development Plan for Calatrava District I, ensuring that interventions are responsive to the actual needs of its teachers and contribute to sustained professional growth, well-being, and retention.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

- 1. Schools Division of Negros Occidental.** Continue promoting teachers' mental and emotional health through stress reduction and wellness programs. Provide additional resources for professional development, implement further policies to reduce non-teaching administrative workloads, and consider hiring additional non-teaching personnel in schools with high workload demands.
- 2. District Supervisors.** Continue institutionalizing stress reduction programs and recognition systems, such as wellness workshops and awards for exemplary performance, to sustain teacher morale and promote a positive work environment.

3. **School Administrators.** Maintain professional development programs, effective workload distribution, and support wellness initiatives. Emphasize compliance with policies that reduce administrative burden to teachers' well-being, motivation, satisfaction, and stability.
4. **Teachers.** Actively participate in professional development and school initiatives, practice self-care, collaborate with colleagues, and provide constructive feedback to administrators to sustain motivation, skills, and commitment.
5. **Future Researchers.** Replicate this study in other rural districts, include additional variables such as leadership style, organizational climate, job performance, compensation and benefits, and consider qualitative methods to explore teachers lived experiences with administrative support and policy changes.

PROPOSED FACULTY DEVELOPMENT PLAN (FDP)

This Faculty Development Plan is proposed to sustain the level of Administrative Support and further enhance teachers' professional contentment and retention based on the findings of the study.

Based on the Study: *Administrative Support and Its Effectiveness on Teachers' Professional Contentment and Retention.*

Locale: Calatrava District I

Target Group: 262 Public Elementary School Teachers

General Objective

To strengthen the professional contentment, motivation and retention of teachers through effective administrative support in professional opportunities, workload management and stress reduction interventions.

Specific Objectives

1. Enhance professional skills through continuous learning and mentoring opportunities.
2. Improve workload management practices to prevent burnout and stress.
3. Promote mental, emotional, and physical well-being through wellness programs.
4. Increase motivation, satisfaction, and retention of school personnel.
5. Strengthen collaborative culture and continuous professional growth through PLCs and LACs.

PMES Key Result Area (KRA)

- Content Knowledge and Pedagogy → KRA 1
- Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners → KRA 2
- Curriculum Planning, Assessment, and Reporting → KRA 3
- Community Engagement and Professional Collaboration → KRA 4
- Personal Growth and Professional Development → KRA 5

Faculty Development Plan Discussion

The Faculty Development Plan (FDP) for Calatrava District I is designed to enhance teacher professional contentment and retention through effective administrative support. With a total estimated budget of **₱ 350,000.00**, the allocation per teacher is approximately **₱ 1, 336.64** FOR 262 TEACHERS, ensuring equitable and practical distribution of resources. The FDP addresses key areas identified in the study, linking objectives and activities to measurable IPCRF domains and performances indicators.

Key Area: Professional Development

Table 1. Key Area: Professional Development

Key Area	Objective	Activities	Persons Responsible	Time Frame	Expected Output	PMES KRA	PMES Performance Indicator
Professional Development	Improve teaching competence, knowledge, and instructional practice	In-service training (INSET) on teaching strategies and curriculum updates, lesson planning, and assessment design Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions Classroom observation with coaching and feedback Scholarship/graduate studies orientation ICT & blended learning workshops	District Supervisor, School Heads, Master Teachers	Quarterly	Demonstrates mastery of subject matter; Applies effective instructional strategies; Prepares lessons aligned with curriculum; Participates in at least 1 professional development per quarter	KRA 1, KRA 3, KRA 5	Demonstrates mastery of subject matter and pedagogical content Designs and implements lesson plans aligned with curriculum standards Develops and uses appropriate assessment tools Participates in continuous professional development activities Applies new knowledge and skills to improve teaching practice
ESTIMATED BUDGET ALLOCATION: ₱ 120,000.00 (₱ 458.00 PER TEACHER)							

Objective: Improve teaching competence and knowledge

Activities:

- INSET on teaching strategies and curriculum updates
- Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions
- Classroom observation with coaching and feedback
- Scholarship/graduate studies orientation
- ICT and blended learning workshops

Discussion:

This allocation provides teachers with opportunities to enhance subject knowledge, adopt effective strategies, and remain updated on innovations. It fosters professional mastery, continuous learning, and higher motivation, directly contributing to improved teaching competence and instructional performance.

Key Area: Workload Management

Table 2. Key Area: Workload Management

Key Area	Objective	Activities	Persons Responsible	Time Frame	Expected Output	PMES KRA	PMES Performance Indicator
Workload Management	Reduce stress caused by excessive administrative and non-teaching tasks	Review and analyze teacher workload Removal of non-teaching tasks Clear task assignment and delegation system AO II supports documentation and reporting tasks	School Heads, AO II	Every semester	Balanced workload; ≥90% of teachers report manageable tasks; Improved productivity	KRA 2, KRA 4,	Manages teaching and non-teaching tasks efficiently Completes required tasks within prescribed timelines Demonstrates effective time management and prioritization Maintains productivity without compromising instructional quality
ESTIMATED BUDGET ALLOCATION: ₱ 30,000.00 (₱ 114.50 PER TEACHER)							

Objective: Reduce stress caused by excessive administrative and non-teaching tasks.

Activities:

- Review and analyze teacher workload
- Removal of non-teaching tasks
- Clear task assignment and delegation system

➤ AO II supports documentation and reporting tasks

Discussion:

By balancing workload and reducing non-teaching duties, teachers can focus on instruction, maintain a healthy work-life balance, and experience reduced burnout. Efficient task management enhances productivity and overall job satisfaction, supporting long-term retention.

Key Area: Stress Reduction and Wellness

Table 3. Key Area: Stress Reduction and Wellness

Key Area	Objective	Activities	Persons Responsible	Time Frame	Expected Output	PMES KRA	PMES Performance Indicator
Stress Reduction & Wellness	Promote mental, emotional, and physical well-being	Stress management seminars	Guidance Counselor, School Heads, District Nurses	Quarterly / Monthly	≥85% of participants reported reduced stress; Improved attendance and engagement; Documented participation in wellness activities	KRA 2, KRA 5	Demonstrates resilience and emotional regulation at work
		Wellness days, physical activities, team-building exercises Counseling referrals and mental health support Health monitoring and routine check-ups Vaccination and preventive health programs					Actively participates in wellness and stress-management activities Maintains regular attendance and work engagement Sustains personal well-being while meeting professional responsibilities
ESTIMATED BUDGET ALLOCATION: ₱ 50,000.00 (₱ 190.84 PER TEACHER)							

Objective: Promote mental, emotional, and physical well-being

Activities:

- Stress management seminars
- Wellness days, physical activities, team-building exercise
- Counselling referrals and mental health support
- Health monitoring and routine check-ups
- Vaccination and preventive health programs

Discussion:

These initiatives support teacher resilience, motivation, and overall health. Addressing mental, emotional, and physical well-being ensures teachers remain engaged and capable of performing effectively, critical for sustained professional contentment and retention.

Key Area: Recognition and Motivation

Table 4. Key Area: Recognition and Motivation

Key Area	Objective	Activities	Persons Responsible	Time Frame	Expected Output	PMES KRA	PMES Performance Indicator
Recognition & Motivation	Increase teacher engagement, motivation, and retention	Teacher / Staff of the Month/Year awards	School Heads, PTA, AO II	Semi-annual / Monthly	At least 80% of participation, improvement in motivation and retention scores in annual survey	KRA 4, KRA 5	Consistently demonstrates commitment to duties and responsibilities
		Appreciation and recognition ceremonies Performance-based incentives					Shows initiative and positive work attitude Maintains high level of motivation and engagement Contributes to a positive and supportive school culture
ESTIMATED BUDGET ALLOCATION: ₱ 25,000.00 (₱ 95.42 PER TEACHER)							

Objective: Increase teacher engagement, motivation, and retention

Activities:

- Teacher of the Month and Year awards
- Appreciation and recognition ceremonies
- Performance-based incentives

Discussion:

Recognition initiatives foster morale, encourage high performance, and strengthen commitment to teaching roles. Acknowledging contributions motivates teachers and reinforces a culture of excellence.

Key Area: Mentoring and Coaching

Table 5. Key Area: Mentoring and Coaching

Key Area	Objective	Activities	Persons Responsible	Time Frame	Expected Output	PMES KRA	PMES Performance Indicator
Mentoring & Coaching	Develop professional growth and collaborative culture, and curriculum competence	Peer coaching and mentoring programs Master teachers and senior staff to guide new teachers Action research and collaborative projects Lesson planning review and assessment coaching	School Heads, Master Teachers, District Supervisor	Ongoing / Quarterly	75% of new teachers paired with mentors; Documented improvement in instructional practice, lessons and assessments improved per coaching feedback	KRA 1, KRA 2, KRA 3, KRA 5	Provides instructional guidance and support to colleagues Engages in mentoring and peer coaching activities Improves lesson delivery and assessment practices based on feedback Demonstrates collaboration and professional leadership
ESTIMATED BUDGET ALLOCATION: ₱ 25,000.00 (₱ 95.42 PER TEACHER)							

Objectives: Develop professional growth and collaborative culture

Activities:

- Peer coaching and mentoring programs
- Master teachers and senior staff guide new teachers
- Action research and collaborative projects

Discussion:

Structured mentoring supports professional development, encourages collaborative learning, and cultivates a culture of continuous improvement. Teachers benefit from guidance, shared expertise, and opportunities to enhance their practice.

Key Areas: Monitoring and Evaluation

Table 6. Key Areas: Monitoring and Evaluation

Key Area	Objective	Activities	Persons Responsible	Time Frame	Expected Output	PMES KRA	PMES Performance Indicator
Monitoring & Evaluation	Ensure effectiveness of faculty development program	Feedback surveys PMES-based performance reviews Retention tracking and well-being monitoring	School Heads, District Supervisor	End of School Year	Evidence-based implemented; ≥80% of activities rated effective by participants; Sustained professional contentment; Retention rates maintained or improved	KRA 3, KRA 5	Uses performance data and feedback to improve practice Participates in PMES performance reviews and evaluations Monitors progress toward professional and organizational goals Demonstrates accountability for performance outcomes
ESTIMATED BUDGET ALLOCATION: ₱ 25,000.00 (₱ 95.42 PER TEACHER)							

Objectives: Ensure effectiveness of faculty development program

Activities:

- Feedback surveys from teachers
- Performance reviews and IPCRF integration
- Retention tracking and well-being monitoring

Discussion:

Systematic monitoring ensures FDP effectiveness, allows evidence-based adjustments, and promotes sustained teacher satisfaction and retention. Feedback and performance data provide actionable insights for continuous improvement.

Key Area: Professional Learning Communities (PLC)

Table 7. Key Areas: Key Area: Professional Learning Communities (PLC)

Key Area	Objective	Activities	Persons Responsible	Time Frame	Expected Output	PMES KRA	PMES Performance Indicator
Professional Learning Communities (PLC)	Encourage continuous professional collaboration	Collaborative lesson planning Sharing best practices and innovative teaching strategies Joint problem-solving for school challenges	Teachers, School Heads, AO II	Monthly	Stronger teamwork, innovation in teaching, enhanced instructional practices	KRA 1, KRA 3, KRA 5	Actively participates in collaborative planning and problem-solving Shares best practices and instructional strategies Contributes to team-based outputs such as lesson plans and assessments Applies collaborative learning to improve classroom practice
ESTIMATED BUDGET ALLOCATION: ₱ 50,000.00 (₱ 190.84 PER TEACHER)							

Objective: Encourage continuous professional collaboration

Activities:

- Collaborative lesson planning
- Sharing best practices and innovative teaching strategies
- Joint problem-solving for school challenges

Discussion:

PLCs enhance teamwork, innovation, and instructional quality, supporting a collaborative professional environment. Teachers share strategies, solve challenges collectively, and engage in reflective practice, fostering continuous growth.

Contingency Plan

Objective: Ensure that expected needs, emergencies or additional support requirements do not disrupt FDP implementation.

Strategies:

1. Set aside 5-10% of total budget to cover:

- Extra training materials or venue cost
- Replacement or supplementary facilitators
- Unplanned wellness or health-related activities

2. **Flexible scheduling of activities:** LAC, PLCs, or wellness sessions can be adjusted based on school calendar changes.
3. **Periodic review of Expenditures:** Surpluses can be relocated to underfunded activities.
4. **Alternative delivery modes:** Online platforms for trainings or seminars if face-to-face sessions are disrupted.
5. **Approval and reporting:** Contingency spending must be approved by the School Head or District Supervisor and documented for transparency.

Expected Outcomes:

1. Sustained Very High level of administrative support.
2. Improved teachers' motivation, satisfaction, and well-being.
3. Strong retention and commitment across school personnel.
4. Healthier, more productive, and collaborative school environment.
5. PMES alignment ensures measurable professional growth and improved performance.

Rationale

1. Activities are directly linked to study findings showing that administrative support strongly improves professional contentment and retention.
2. Professional development, workload management, and wellness programs enhance competencies, well-being and performance, aligned with PMES KRAs 1, 2, and 5
3. Recognition, mentoring, and PLCs reinforce motivation, collaboration, and professional engagement, aligned with PMES KRAs 4 and 5, supporting sustainable teacher performance and retention.
4. Budget allocations ensure feasibility, equitable, and prioritize high-impact areas, ensuring activities can be monitored and evaluated using PMES performance indicators and Means of Verification (MOVs).

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